

Rentier States and the Transition Away From Oil: Oman, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

This paper examines the recent movements to transition away from oil in the Gulf Cooperation Council immediately following the oil price crash of 2014. To provide a useful frame of analysis, we examine the oil production of state-owned firms in Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Oman through the lens of the microeconomic shutdown rule. This reveals that these states have entered a phase where they wish to exit the market in the long run, but maintain operations in the short run, as operations still yield an immediate accounting profit. We find that the drive to transition was created by a fall in average oil price to around USD \$50 a barrel. We also find that this process is significantly hampered by the strong presence of the so-called ‘authoritarian bargain’ in these countries, whereby governments reduce austerity measures and taxation in order to maintain popularity. As the world lessens its reliance on fossil fuels, we examine the dilemma faced by oil dependent states: they must choose to either lose political capital in an attempt to become economically sustainable or risk the oil rents that sustain their regimes drying up.

Rentier States and the Transition Away From Oil: Oman, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia

As the world pushes to transition to a post-carbon future, the countries of the Gulf warrant particular attention. Their extreme reliance on fossil fuel rents and lack of dynamism in their private sectors signals that transitioning away from carbon-extractive economies will be a herculean task. An analysis of their transition plans, however, shows both a failure to complete their own listed goals and a worrying continuation of oil and natural gas dependence. This paper adapts the microeconomic shutdown rule to account for governments who rely on extractive firms for income and uses this framework to examine why states reliant on revenues from natural resources have difficulty weaning their economies off of resource extraction, why the Gulf in particular is hesitant to do so, and what this may mean for the future of governance in the region.

The history of oil production and the governments that rely upon it in the Middle East present difficulties to transitioning away from reliance on fossil fuels. Government support of key industries in the region begins with state-led development, pioneered by Mustafa Kemal Ataturk in the 1920s, which rose to popularity across the region as young governments adopted import substitution industrialization policies. States attempted to reduce reliance on former colonizers by placing tariffs on imports and subsidizing domestic producers and manufacturers. Oil producing nations redistributed wealth in the form of investment in education and health infrastructure, subsidies, and lucrative public sector jobs. Through these decades of state-centric policy in the 60s and 70s, Gulf monarchies required little to no income tax revenue to fund their operations. Political society remained stable through the social contract of the authoritarian bargain, wherein individuals forgo political freedoms in return for security and wealth distribution (Desai, Olofsgard, and Yousef 2009). Citizens got used to a one-way flow of cash from state coffers to citizens' pockets, so that austerity measures were politically out of the

question. Even in the 80s, when oil prices tanked, Gulf countries preferred to rack up debt rather than cut government spending or expand state capacity to tax the citizenry. The 2008 recession also depressed oil prices and subsequently placed pressure on GCC monarchies as dwindling revenues were expected to maintain extensive government services according to the social contract. According to the US Energy Information Administration, crude oil prices dropped from about \$134 per barrel in July 2008 to \$39 per barrel in February of 2009 (EIA, 2021). Most recently, advances in horizontal drilling and hydraulic fracturing (fracking) technology made recovery of shale oil economically feasible. This caused a supply shock as non-OPEC producers entered the petrochemical market with full force and struck away much of OPEC's pricing power (Berk, Istemi, and Eren Çam). The OPEC+ agreement (led by Saudi Arabia and Russia) concentrated some pricing power, but non-affiliated producers still pushed prices downward, creating the modern oil market, which can be modeled as oligopolistic competition.

A limited number of powerful states and companies are influential in the market, and they compete in a similar fashion to each other. However, governments face additional fixed costs on top of regular firm operating costs. These include civil servants' paychecks, infrastructure projects, and rent distribution through social spending, all of which have come to be expected across GCC states under the authoritarian bargain (Desai, Olofsgard, and Yousef 2009). Due to the dip in oil prices at the onset of the COVID pandemic in 2020, oil producing states are once again forced to run unsustainable deficits in the short run in order to avoid political unrest and instability through social spending and handouts. In the long run, however, Gulf monarchies have set a series of goals and visions to pivot their economies away from the oil market and towards more sustainable sectors. Oman, Saudi Arabia, and Kuwait have all released

national plans for rebuilding their economies around commerce, industry, tourism and service sectors.

Conceptual Framework

The microeconomic shutdown rule claims that a firm will continue operating in the short run if prices sit below average total cost but above average variable cost. In the long run, however, this set of conditions will force the firm to shut down. We claim that this theory can be applied to Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Oman's governments, where average fixed costs include government expenditures. This explains GCC countries' proposed shifts away from *rentierism*, or a reliance on oil rents for government revenue. In the short run, rentier states run budget deficits to keep their civil servants on the payroll and maintain the crony capitalist system that ensures government stability. In the long run, however, Saudi Arabia has recognized that volatile oil revenues will become smaller and more unstable over time. Where economic boom times of high oil prices could previously be expected to erase the consequences of periods of debt, the imbalance of payments in rentier states has become unsustainable. This realization has led to the proposed reduction in reliance on oil revenues in favor of manufacturing, construction, tourism, and knowledge industries (Hameed 2020). This diversification is essentially a gradual "shut down" over the long term.

We posit that oil-producing nations operate in a monopolistic competitive oil market and face higher economic costs of operation than non-state firms. Gulf nations operate similarly to monopolistically competitive firms; however, they must fulfill their side of the social contract, providing subsidized utilities, lucrative public sector jobs, and free education and healthcare for citizens. The differing costs of operation suggest that oil-producing states cannot operate profitably in more competitive oil markets. This unprofitability, however, may not cause them to

cease oil production. By applying the shutdown rule to the operation of oil-producing states, we find that oil-states face a trade-off between a short-term reduction in fixed costs and long term economic sustainability through economic transition. This theory is based on several underlying factors and assumptions about the oil market and crude oil producing states.

The first underlying assumption of our theory is that the global oil market is an oligopolistic competition. Oligopolies are created by several factors, most notably limited entry and exit in the market, the existence of a small number of powerful producers, and restricted production. The crude oil market is dominated by several large firms and oil producing states that control large portions of the global supply. Along with the small number of market players, a large group of oil producers belong to the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). These states collude to restrict the global oil supply and keep prices high. With such large market players and so much power concentrated in OPEC, any new player trying to enter the crude oil market faces high barriers to entry. In 2017, OPEC countries including Saudi Arabia and Russia began programs to restrict production (OPEC 2017). Higher competition in the market, however, drove them to restrict production less than they would if they had total oligopolistic power (Berk 2020). This would suggest the market is not entirely a collusive oligopoly. Therefore, our understanding is that the market for crude oil can be treated as being in oligopolistic competition.

To graphically represent this market, we chose to use kinked marginal revenue (MR) and average revenue (AR) curves. These kinked curves represent the oligopolistic competitive oil market faced by major market players. In this market, if one firm lowers its prices, the others must as well, or else buyers will purchase from the competition and the higher priced firm will lose revenue. This is especially true in the crude oil market, where crude oil products are

near-perfect substitutes for one another. When price movement of this kind occurs, the global oil price shifts; however, the share of demand going to each firm does not change, since all of these firms share the same price. OPEC and OPEC-aligned countries try to address this issue by raising the price collectively to ensure no firm forces all the other firms to lower their prices. As we will see, however, their capacity to do this was reduced in 2014, when American shale oil producers began exporting oil at lower average prices.

Our second assumption is that an oil-producing state operates differently from a competitive oil-producing firm. This is based on rentier theory, but it can be simply explained using economic theory. A competitive firm in the global oil market operates like any firm in monopolistic competition. As can be seen in figure 1, a firm can be defined by its average total cost (ATC), average fixed cost (AFC), marginal cost (MC), kinked average revenue (AR), and kinked marginal revenue (MR) curves. In figure 1 we can see a graphical representation of this kind of firm. Figure 1 shows a profitable firm operating at an ATC significantly below the average revenue. Area A represents the profit of the firm by showing the margin between costs and average revenue by the quantity sold. We theorize that oil-producing states face similar or identical economic costs of operation, with one major exception: oil-producing states must fund their government budgets with their oil revenues. Assuming that average government expenditure (AGE) is fairly stable over time, we can add AGE to AFC and create a new graphical representation of the operations of an oil-producing state. Figure 2 shows that these additional costs create a problem for the oil-producing state. The much higher costs of running a country as opposed to a firm can cause these governments to operate at an economic loss. Area A in Figure 2 represents the losses incurred by the state as government expenditures exceed oil revenues, equal to the margin between cost and price multiplied by the quantity sold. It is

important to point out that on paper, these governments' oil production companies may be operating at an accounting profit. However, the non-governmental firms and the oil-producing state face very different economic costs of operation. This is the fundamental difference that we assume differentiates firms and oil-producing states.

Figure 1

The Oligopolistically Competitive Oil Producing Firm

Figure 2

The Oligopolistically Competitive Oil-Producing State

Government expenditures per capita around the GCC reliably include the costs of maintaining the so-called ‘authoritarian bargain,’ including high levels of investment into infrastructure and education, subsidies on consumer goods, and lucrative public sector jobs. This makes these states accrue substantial fixed costs that a firm does not face. This difference is shown in figures 1 and 2: the competitive firm has average fixed costs that put its profit maximization point at the break-even point.

Gulf governments may have announced their intentions to diversify their economies, or “shut down”; however, their present failure to meet stated goals suggests that governments are

delaying the transition away from oil in order to avoid political turmoil. Imposing taxes and cutting government spending will undoubtedly create a public desire for greater accountability and challenge current rulers' legitimacy.

Literature Review

Economic and Political Characteristics of Oil-Based Economies

All GCC states, including Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Kuwait, derive a large share of their economic output from oil. These states are all monarchies with relatively small citizenries (referred to as "labor poor") and undiversified economies. However, the empirical evidence suggests that these states are highly heterogeneous entities, and the economic impacts of oil in each state are fairly unique (Nusair 2019, Nasir 2019). Macroeconomic indicators are heavily tied to the price of oil in these countries. The main macroeconomic factors investigated by the literature were inflation, the balance of trade, and GDP. The literature tends to agree that across these states, these macroeconomic factors are positively affected by increased oil prices. The main variation between these states is the duration and intensity of the effect of oil prices on these indicators.

As a rule, OPEC states tend to experience periods of GDP growth in response to higher oil prices (Rebeca and Sánchez 2005). GDP growth in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (henceforth referred to as the KSA) shows a significant positive correlation with positive oil price shocks (Nasir 2019). As one of the largest exporters of oil in the world, the KSA benefits from price shocks that increase export revenues and improve its trade balance. The KSA's inflation rates seem to also respond to both rising and falling oil prices; a similar effect is found in Kuwaiti inflation rates. Kuwait's GDP seems to similarly respond positively to growth in oil prices, and their balance of trade responds to oil shocks just as strongly. The main difference in Kuwait is

that shocks have longer lasting effects, which holds for most smaller oil-producing nations (Nasir 2019). Nusair (2019) also found that Oman is the only state in the GCC that experiences deflationary effects when oil prices fall. Oman's GDP growth stands out as one of the most affected by oil shocks relative to other states (Nasir 2019). The country also experiences some of the longest-lasting effects of oil shocks, even when compared to Kuwait. The findings in these areas show clear distinctions between Kuwait, KSA, and Oman which give us an opportunity to explore why transition plans pursued by these states vary in effectiveness and aim.

States' reactions to oil price shocks can be explained by several measurements: the relative volume of a state's oil production, the proportion of government expenditure funded by oil revenues, the size of currency reserves, savings mechanisms, and sovereign wealth funds (Nusair 2019, 2016, Nasir 2019). When countries have low savings and a high proportion of government expenditure funded by oil revenues, their output is highly vulnerable to the volatility of the oil market. The volume of oil production in relative terms also indicates how much market power a state has over oil pricing. Savings mechanisms, like wealth funds and currency reserves, help states reduce the effects of inflation and perpetuate the economic effects of a price shock over a longer period of time. Together, these factors provide a foundation for our analysis of the differences between transitional pressures on these various economies.

Effects of Rentierism on Studied Countries

GCC countries— and oil producing states in general— harbor a strong incentive to exploit their natural resource wealth, and tend to do so through monopolistic, state-owned companies. This is indicative of a rentier state, where public ownership and control of the oil sector allows extraction and redistribution of rents as governments see fit. Literature surrounding rentier states links such governance to “authoritarianism, poor government performance, lagging

economic development, (and) severe social disparities” (Jenkins et al. 2011). When the state is the dominant actor in the political economy and its revenue can be drawn almost entirely from resource rents (as has been the case in almost all Gulf countries), there is an incentive to create an “allocation state”. In this scenario, rent money is redistributed to co-opt political and economic elites and appease (or oppress) the masses through food subsidies, health and education programs, and expansion of lucrative public sector jobs (Jenkins et al. 2011, pg 5). This can all be achieved without building up a productive state with efficient investment since the state is indirectly taxing the populace (Auty and Gelb 2001).

The resource curse paradigm describes the large flow of capital directed at a single sector at the expense of others. This theory works in parallel with Dutch Disease theory, which describes the phenomenon of domestic currency appreciation that renders non-tradable goods less competitive. Both can lead to contractions in agriculture and industrial sectors, creating a vicious cycle of reliance on oil rents to operate the government and its characteristically large social support net (Auty and Gelb 2001). Indeed, GCC nations have often suffered fiscal deficits and balance of payment problems as a result of fluctuating oil prices (Hameed 2020).

Politically, the tight concentration of wealth associated with government ownership of oil, as in Saudi Aramco, can incite fears of unstable governance associated with concentrated power. Latin America hosts examples of violent revolution after violent revolution as different factions compete for control of rents. The Gulf, however, has surprised resource curse pundits with its relative stability and profitable state-owned enterprises. Camett et al. and Auty and Gelb cite crony capitalism as one of the main drivers of stability in the Gulf, but Steffen Hertog believes that Gulf rentier monarchies have successfully managed profit and market oriented public companies. Hertog notes that many public players in the Gulf, including Saudi Arabia’s

Basic Industries Corporation (SABIC), may act as monopolies, but they remain competitive in liberalized domestic markets and on a global scale (Hertog 2010, 262).

Although rentier states across the Middle East, Latin America, and North Africa display dictatorial tendencies, there are notable exceptions to the “resource curse” theory. Norway, for example, boasts a strong democracy, rule of law, and reliable institutions. The country is the 8th largest natural gas and twelfth largest oil producer globally (Kasprzyk 2011), and according to the Organization of Economic Complexity, Norway drew 47% of its export revenues from petroleum products in 2020. The secret to Norway’s success lies in its established institutions whereby authorities were directly accountable to the people (Kasprzyk 2011). Upon the discovery of oil, Norwegian authorities founded a vast sovereign wealth fund instead of allocating oil revenues to shorter-term projects. The Government Pension Fund, established in 1990, aimed to distribute oil revenues throughout the Norwegian population and across generations. The fund serves as a financial reserve and a long term savings plan with strict government guidelines that limit withdrawals to only 4% every year. Economic planners sacrificed immediate GDP growth for a more sustained, long-term investment into equities, fixed income, real estate and renewable energy infrastructure (Norges Bank Investment Management, 2019). As a result, Norway has avoided the boom-and-bust cycle associated with Dutch Disease and now boasts one of the highest standards of living worldwide (Kasprzyk 2011).

Given the increasing level of competition in oil markets, and the GCC’s growing debts, scholars and gulf authorities sense that this current political stability may not be sustainable. According to a variance decomposition study by Najla Almutairi, the majority of Saudi unemployment fluctuations are directly related to oil price shocks (Almutairi 2020). The oil reserves of Bahrain, Oman, and Qatar could only last for a few more decades at current

production and consumption levels according to Hameed 2020. Oil price volatility and demand shocks in oil both place GCC economies under considerable stress, contributing to the various plans to diversify previously oil-dominated economies in Saudi Arabia, Kuwait and Oman.

Transitions

The literature surrounding the policies of the three countries examined strongly suggests that oil rentierism creates institutional and economic barriers to transition that far exceed that of other countries transitioning into high levels of development. Beyond sharing similar cultures and authoritarian tendencies, Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Kuwait all have extremely small private sectors, employing 30 percent, 18 percent, and 11 percent of native laborers respectively. All three have presented ambitious plans to diversify revenue streams, shift employment to the private sector, and reform institutions to improve ease of doing business, and all three have fallen behind on benchmarks for achieving these goals (Grand and Wolff 2020; Al-Malawi et al. 2016; Carvalho et al. 2017). Examining what their transition plans have in common, how they differ, and how they have fared in achieving them can give valuable insight into the barriers that rentierism - particularly rentierism in absolutist regimes - creates for sustainable economic growth.

As the Gulf's most populous country and largest economy (excluding Iran), the KSA has generated by far the largest amount of literature in assessing its ability to transition beyond rent reliance. The country faced massive starting barriers in shifting away from oil, with the GCC's characteristic small private sector, budgetary reliance on oil rents, and problematic regulatory framework discouraging development in the non-oil sector (Al-Kibsi et al, 2015). However, the nation has aggressively marketed its 'Vision 2030' diversification program, touting massive infrastructure projects and urban development as it pours more and more resources into

privatization and financial risk reduction. The state has laid out meticulously detailed economic goals, provided plans of action for areas requiring more technical policy, and identified key sectors and sub-sectors in completing its transition. Despite all of these attempts, however, it is falling massively short. The nation's autocratic status has put a damper on development outside of the oil sector - nearly all of the FDI entering the country in recent years has been towards fossil fuels (Lloyd's Bank, 2021). Unless the Saudi economy can complete a massive turnaround in the next fifteen years, an unsustainable level of government debt is almost inevitable (Grand, 2020).

Our assessment of GCC countries is rounded out by two smaller states on separate development paths: Oman and Kuwait. Both are even more heavily reliant on fossil fuel rents than Saudi Arabia: 89% of Kuwait's government revenue comes from oil rents alone (Carvalho, 2017), and 84.7% of Oman's comes from its fossil fuel exports (Al-Mawali, 2016). However, the two are polar opposites in terms of policy. Oman has been relatively proactive in planning for an economy without oil, laying out plans for its future as a transport hub and exporter of renewable energy. However, its plan is quite vague, with its goals being either extremely broad or unhelpfully ambitious (Sultanate of Oman 2021). Kuwait, on the other hand, was a relatively late adopter of a diversification policy: their transition plan, the National Program for Economic and Financial Stability, came in 2017, but contained specific action items on how to reform Kuwait's byzantine and lagging bureaucracy, as well as targeted goals for growing the entrepot's financial sector (Carvalho, 2017). Despite their differing and innovative approaches, however, the two states are both lagging far behind in their goals, creating a uniform outcome of failure across the GCC. As concerning as this may be, such failures provide wider opportunities to examine what has and has not been effective regarding policies and action in the shift away from oil rentierism.

The state remains the central actor in gulf political economies. Private endowments called “*awkwaf*” used to play a prominent role in the region; however, state investment largely displaced these upon the discovery of oil. The government similarly crowds out many industries in the GCC, including construction, fuel distribution, and insurance (Kabbani and Ben Mimoune 2022). Private businesses have played a larger role in education, health care, infrastructure, water, energy, and transport facilities since the 90s; however, much of these projects are still dependent on government-funded projects and consumption. Many of the private gulf businesses that have expanded overseas are propped up by government subsidies and support (Kabbani and Ben Mimoune 2022).

Many Gulf states, including Kuwait, Oman, and the KSA, lack a substantial national working class, and most nationals are still directly employed by the government (Kabbani and Ben Mimoune 2022). According to the Middle East Institute, the Saudi business sector displays a lack of “expertise, managerial structures, and capacity for long-term planning” (Ackerman 2022). Kabbani and Ben Mimoune argue that transition cannot take place without redefining the current political economy. With so much of this new, nominally “private” activity reliant on petroleum wealth, any real transition away from an oil-dependent economy would weaken the social contract through which Gulf governments channel petroleum wealth to nationals (Kabbani and Ben Mimoune 2022).

Data

The variables we intended to examine in this paper were government debt and oil revenues. Oman, KSA, and Kuwait all produce these figures publicly to varying degrees, but we relied on international organizations to aggregate and normalize this data. For debt data, the International Monetary Fund produces total government debt data for all of these countries going

back to 2000 (International Monetary Fund). Government oil rent data is produced by the World Bank.

Figure 3

Oil Rents as a % of GDP

Note. Adapted from *Crude Oil Prices: West Texas Intermediate (WTI) - Cushing, Oklahoma*, by The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 1986.

Figure 4

Crude Oil Prices

Note. Adapted from *Crude Oil Prices: West Texas Intermediate (WTI) - Cushing, Oklahoma*, by The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 1986.

All of our data is annualized, as this is the level at which governments consistently report data. This also conveniently provides us with less volatility than would exist at the weekly or daily levels. Despite the annual reporting periods, large year-on-year volatility in the data does still exist. This, however, is simply a reflection of the dramatic volatility of oil markets underlying the finances of these governments.

All of these measures of government performance need to also be put up against the aforementioned oil prices, both to show correlation and patterns in oil prices that might force certain decisions to be made.

Analysis

To examine the variables we obtained, we used three simple methods of analysis. First, we plotted our variables against each other and crude oil price over the same period of time to look for patterns. Second, we ran the correlation coefficient of the data against an annualized oil price. Finally, we compared the graphs to the important policy decision dates that we found connected to each country's oil transition. Our analysis was done through the lens of our conceptual framework.

Comparative Analysis

Comparing oil rents, government expenditure, and oil prices, we can see several patterns in the data. Government debt in Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA all declined between 2002 and 2014. This is also a period of relatively high oil prices and high oil rents. The mean values from each of the graphs for the two periods are enumerated in Table 1. We can see that the average

level of debt decreased in these countries when the oil price was, on average, around 74 dollars a barrel. During that same period, debts fell when the average oil rents as a percent of GDP were slightly lower. The large fall in oil prices in 2008 dramatically reduced oil rents as a percentage of GDP, but only caused a very slight jump in debt as a percentage of GDP in these states.

Table 1

Averaged Indicators of Periods Surrounding 2003-2014 and of the Period 2003-2014.

Period	Average Debt as % of GDP	Average Oil Price (USD)	Average Oil Rents as % of GDP
2000-2002 and 2015-2019	47.8	52.5	47.9
2003-2014	12.9	74.0	44.7

Indebtedness in all states only began to trend upward in 2014. This corresponds to a price collapse that brought the average price of a barrel of oil down to 52.93 USD from 2014-2019. These data suggest that temporary volatile movements of the oil price do not directly affect the indebtedness of the Omani, Kuwaiti, and KSA governments in relative terms. However, government debt as a percentage of GDP does seem to respond to multi-year changes in average oil prices. When oil's average price rises above about an average of 52 USD these states begin to cover debts and make money. When it sits at around that price, these states begin to take on debt or maintain higher percentages of debt to GDP, as is the case with Kuwait from 2016-2019.

It is also notable that, compared to the KSA and Kuwait, Oman's growth in debt to GDP ratio has been significantly faster. Given Oman's slightly lower per capita oil revenues, they likely have less price cushion before they begin to run into the point where AGE brings the ATC above ATR. The rapid growth of Omani debt to GDP, therefore, is a result of the state 'living closer to the edge' when it comes to oil revenues.

Correlation Coefficients

Our second method of analysis was to examine the correlation between oil prices and the rent and debt indicators. We used RStudio's `cor()` function to calculate the correlation coefficient for each variable and for each state with oil prices. The results are listed below in table 2.

Table 2 shows that there is a strongly negative correlation between the level of debt Kuwait and the KSA face and the oil price — when oil prices rise, debts fall and vice versa. This makes logical sense and reflects what we would expect from a government that funds its operations through oil rents. Oman experiences this negative effect as well, although the correlation is not as strong. When it comes to the oil rents of these states, the correlation coefficient is less certain. What is consistent is the positive relationship between oil rents and the oil price. This would make sense, as when oil prices rise we would expect the oil rents of the government to increase as a percentage of GDP. One reason these correlations might not be as strong, however, is that since these countries' GDP's might be highly correlated with oil prices, the rise in oil rents is closely proportional to the rise in GDP. This would reduce fluctuation and give us lower correlation coefficients across the board.

Figure 5

Total Government Debt for General Government, Oil Rents, Crude Oil Prices: West Texas

Intermediate

Note. Adapted from *Crude Oil Prices: West Texas Intermediate (WTI) - Cushing, Oklahoma*, by The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 1986.

Table 2

Variable Correlation Coefficients

Country : Indicator	Debt to Oil Price	Oil Rent to Oil Price
Oman	-0.45	0.31
Kuwait	-0.83	0.62
KSA	-0.81	0.54
Average	-0.70	0.49

Note. Computed in R, N = 19 for all coefficients

Despite their limitations, these correlations help confirm our findings from the previous section. Debt in these states seems to respond inversely to the change in oil prices over time. Oil rents seem to respond positively to oil rents over time. The data suggest, however, that Oman is slightly different from Kuwait and the KSA - Oman seems to follow the general trend of the other two states, just to a lesser degree.

In Economic and Political Context

Our analysis has found several interesting correlations and simultaneous occurrences in the data we observed. Over the period of analysis, 2000 to 2019, the governments of Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA underwent a period of relative prosperity interrupted by a period of

continuous losses. These phenomena provide us insight on how oil prices affect the operations of these governments, but our understanding is limited unless we put these events into the full political and economic context.

Figure 4

Crude Oil Prices: West Texas Intermediate

The contexts that are important to explore for our analysis occur around the two events of interest noted in our comparative analysis: the large drop in prices between 2008 and 2009 and the large drop in prices between 2014 and 2015. Each of these large drops in the oil prices were the result of different events in the overall economy and oil market. As we saw in our comparative analysis, however, these shocks had very different effects on the indebtedness of the governments of Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA.

The 2008 financial crisis precedes and precipitates the large fall in oil prices between 2008-2009. This large price drop was a result of falling global economic activity. The correlation between global economic performance, or the performance of the largest economies, and oil prices has been found to be consistent (Hamlin 2009, Wang 2017). Essentially, global economic

activity is a predictor of global oil demand: global oil demand fell sharply in 2008 as a result of the financial crisis.

Our data shows that the governments of Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA did not respond to this global economic crisis and drop in oil prices by increasing government debts. Under these circumstances, one might assume that a government would have to take on debts to sustain or stimulate economic activity. There are two explanations to this. Firstly, as mentioned in our comparative analysis, governments only seem to respond to sustained changes in prices. These oil producing governments have the ability to smooth expenditure over a longer period of time regardless of temporary spikes and collapses of the oil price. Another explanation for this is that it was much harder to borrow during the global financial crisis, and these governments simply did not have access to credit they might have wanted to use at the time. The data does suggest the first answer, but it seems unlikely that the second explanation had no effect on these governments at the time.

The 2008-2009 drop in oil prices seems to have been a result of changing global economic activity. This shock seems to have had little effect on any of these governments' bottom line, and in the long run it seems that since Oman, Kuwait, and KSA maintained strong market power, they continued to earn oligopolistic rents that covered government expenditure and kept debt low throughout the high average price period.

This price drop almost immediately began to drive up government debt. Before discussing the differences between 2008 and 2014, changes that occurred between the two shocks should be examined. The Arab spring occurred in 2011, and this caused the governments of these oil producing countries to respond to unrest in their states by increasing the distribution of oil rents to their populations. In 2011 alone, "the Omani government created some 50,000 new

public sector jobs, raised the minimum wage for private sector employees, launched a new unemployment benefit, nearly doubled university enrollments, and increased the monthly stipend for students.” (Calabrese 2018). In the same year, Kuwait put 63 billion USD towards increasing public sector salaries and fuel subsidies (Stack 2011). The KSA’s response to the Arab spring was a 130 billion dollar plan to raise wages, build subsidized housing, and provide unemployment benefits (BBC 2016). At this time, these governments decided to cut into the profits they made from high oligopolistic oil rents and placate the public stirred up by the Arab Spring.

These governments, now on less sound financial footing, and less able to save and smooth income across sudden collapses in revenue, ran headfirst into the 2014-2015 drop in oil prices caused by the United States shale extraction boom. The large expansion in shale oil production caused OPEC nations - especially the KSA - to change their oil production strategy. In 2014, the KSA and several other states decided to let the oil supply increase, as they thought low oil prices would drive the fledgling shale oil industry out of business (Fattouh 2016). However, United States shale producers were not pushed out by this tactic. Realizing this strategy had failed, OPEC announced in 2016 that it was going to cut back on oil production (OPEC 2016). However, the KSA and OPEC more generally seem to have lost some of their market power in the shift (Berk 2020). The KSA and other OPEC nations were no longer able to operate with all their newly encouraged government expenditure at a profit. Our model would suggest it is at this point that, facing a more competitive oligopolistic market and recently increased government expenditures, Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA would enter into a phase of growing debts that represent the micro-economic shut down phase.

While the oil companies of these states might still be profitable, the increasing government debt of all of these states points to an overall failure to profit. When a firm can no longer make economic profit, it has two options: it can shut down and move to another opportunity, or it can persist sustaining losses and hope that business will eventually recover. As explored in our framework, the shutdown rule provides a circumstance in which a firm might still operate at a loss. In those circumstances, operating reduces the amount of debt one would take on since the firm still has to pay fixed costs, like rents, for a contractually set period. In the case of these states, Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA have made explicit contracts for governance at least since 2011 with their citizens. Maintaining these contractual fixed costs in welfare spending is necessary to the continued legitimacy of these states.

With the loss of market power in 2014, Oman, Kuwait, and the KSA entered into the shutdown dilemma. By operating, they reduced the burden of the rents they had to pay, but also continued at an economic loss. The only permanent solution to this problem is to exit the market. Table 3 provides the context of this decision process. Immediately after entering this period of economic losses, the choices that these states make become clear. As our model would predict, these states chose to keep operating their oil industries but began to plan for an exit from this market. Both the KSA and Kuwait announced their plans for a transition away from oil within 3 years of the oil price collapse. Oman's circumstances are slightly different. Having faced fiscal instability in the past due to high oil rents, Oman pledged to try and move away from oil in 1995, likely due to its relatively smaller oil endowment (Calabrese 2018). In 2014, however, Oman began to cut expenditures and rents to its populace as a result of the oil price squeeze. Even with Oman's longer history of transition plans, conditions pushing production into the shutdown

threshold forced a reconsideration of policy. In the political and economic contexts of the period analyzed, these oil rentier states behave in the way our framework predicted.

Table 3

States Oil Transition Timelines

Event	KSA	Oman	Kuwait
Year of First "Vision" Plan	2016	1995	2017
Date of Completion/Goals Set Too	2030	Every 5 Years	2035

Conclusion

The Gulf finds itself in a precarious position. As the world pushes for a transition away from oil, it faces the elimination of by far its largest stream of income – one that its economies have been almost entirely structured around for decades. The very factors that ensured stability and prosperity for these countries have become economic and institutional barriers to an effective pivot. As oil revenues dry up and public debts skyrocket, the Gulf is attempting to quickly and radically transition towards a more sustainable economic model. This narrative leaves an observer with two questions: why did these states choose to transition now, and will these transitions be effective?

We find that the reliance of GCC countries on fossil fuels poses a massive problem for an effective transition. Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Kuwait all have little to no experience with taxation, and have been able to survive up until now almost entirely on oil rents. However, these countries - and the Gulf as a whole - have begun to bump up against the shutdown point in the long run. As their external debts begin to mount and the oil market becomes progressively less

reliable as a source of income, these states have come to realize that their rentier model may no longer be sustainable. Their choice to delay their move away from oil is convincingly explained by an application of the microeconomic shutdown rule and the logic of the crony rentier state. By factoring in government expenditures as fixed costs, the point at which governments must find alternatives to oil rents is significantly higher than the point at which a large private firm would consider closing its doors. Because of this, the nations of the Gulf have jumped at the creation of transition plans, exhibited in documents like KSA's "Vision 2030", Oman's "Vision 2040", and Kuwait's National Program for Economic and Financial Stability.

However, our findings suggest extreme difficulties facing the examined states in completing these transitions. The rentier model that these governments base their social contract off of is largely reflective of the authoritarian bargain: in exchange for authoritarian rule, these states guarantee that the profits of lucrative state-owned oil producers flow directly into a wide and deep social safety net with little to no taxation. These states' actions, however, suggest that this may soon have to change. States are realizing that their rentier model of funding is unsustainable in the long-run, but are staring the limitations of such a model in the face as they attempt to move away from it. KSA, Oman, and Kuwait are all between a rock and a hard place: policymakers in the Gulf will either have to face heavy political instability from weakening the authoritarian bargain or risk fiscal insolvency in the long run. While there is no good solution, policymakers intent on making the transition can work to develop considerable tax infrastructures, freeze public sector wage growth, and subsidize entrepreneurship and domestic industry creation in order to create vibrant and dynamic private sectors. It is also extremely important to lessen the labor market's reliance on public sector jobs and create reliable revenue streams from non-oil sources. While this will inherently weaken the strength of the authoritarian

bargain, it will create a sector capable of supporting itself once the oil money dries up – a worthwhile investment. The transition away from oil will be a difficult one, but states should approach the transition with an understanding that short-term pains are necessary for long-term gains.

The recent surge in oil prices offers gulf states a respite from the pressures to transition they have been facing in recent years. It does not, however, represent a transition in the fundamental threats facing the fossil fuel market. Climate change promises and goals might be temporarily put off as the crisis in Ukraine unfolds over the next months or years, but the underlying issues have not gone away. It is not sustainable to rely on recurring crises to prop up oil prices; furthermore, they do not alter the reliance of Gulf states on commodity markets.

In the face of an uncertain future, a deeper understanding of the rentier systems of Gulf states is needed. Further research into the decision making of Gulf governments would help predict the future of these nations and the oil market as a whole. Access to data from a wider range of time periods and sources would provide more accurate analysis, and an improved model capable of factoring in exogenous events would deepen our understanding of how states react to the global environment surrounding oil. Regardless of research, however, the Gulf and its transition away from oil are sure to warrant particular attention. When the international community eventually turns back to their commitments to a fossil-free future, the Gulf's response will shape the region's future. How that future will be written remains yet to be seen.

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